

Exploiting robotics to assess the effects of fatigue on the human wrist joint

Giulia A. Albanese^{1,2,+,*}, Valeria Falzarano^{1,2,+}, Michael W.R. Holmes³, Pietro Morasso¹ and Jacopo Zenzeri¹

¹Robotics, Brain and Cognitive Sciences (RBCS) Unit, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Genoa, Italy

²Department of Informatics, Bioengineering, Robotics and Systems Engineering (DIBRIS), University of Genoa, Genoa, Italy

³Faculty of Applied Health Sciences, Brock University, St. Catharines, ON, Canada

⁺equally contributed to this work

*corresponding author: giulia.albanese@iit.it

Abstract— Studies have investigated the use of robotic devices for human wrist function assessment. Robot-aided evaluations can provide accurate measurements under repeatable and controlled conditions. Safety can be enhanced by real time assessment of performance and tailoring each task to an individual’s actual wrist function. Additional tools can be synchronized with a robot to expand the set of quantifiable variables. In this work, we exploited these advantages to develop a reliable and comprehensive protocol to investigate the effects of forearm muscle fatigue on wrist mechanical properties, sensorimotor functions, and physiological changes.

Keywords—robotic assessment, human wrist, fatigue, proprioception, joint stiffness

I. INTRODUCTION

Fatigue is a temporary decline in muscle performance associated with intense muscle use. Indicators of muscle fatigue can be observed in the surface electromyogram, as a decrease in the mean frequency of signals, resulting from intra- and extra-cellular pH changes [1]. Although healthy subjects may experience fatigue after maximal or submaximal contractions, an earlier onset for people with neuromuscular diseases severely affects quality of life. Among the effects of fatigue on the wrist joint, short-term changes in isometric force production, biomechanical properties and position sense have never been investigated jointly. In our study, leveraging the advantages associated with the use of a wrist robot [2], we developed a safe, repeatable, and time-constrained protocol to evaluate whether and for how long submaximal dynamic fatigue can affect physiological [3], mechanical [4], and sensorimotor outcomes [5].

II. METHODS

A. Experimental Setup

The experimental setup involved the WristBot [2], a robotic manipulandum that allows wrist movements along three degrees of freedom (DoF), with a $\pm 60^\circ$ range of motion along the flexion-extension (FE) plane. The device is equipped with motors, controlled to oppose or facilitate wrist motion and to compensate gravity and inertia. Angular displacements along each DoF are measured by high-resolution incremental encoders. A custom-made soft-grip sensor is wrapped on the robotic handle to measure grip force. Throughout the study, the sEMG signals of three wrist muscles were recorded using bipolar Ag/AgCl electrodes with a sampling rate of 2048 Hz: the flexor carpi radialis (FCR), the extensor carpi radialis (ECR) and the flexor carpi ulnaris (FCU).

B. Experimental Protocol

Thirteen healthy, right-handed volunteers were recruited to participate in the experimental protocol, which included two sessions over different days. During each session, their right forearm was equipped with bipolar electrodes and fixed to the

robot. Firstly, subjects performed a warm-up session, consisting of a 2-minute tracking task with low level resistive forces. Next, subjects were blindfolded to reduce their cognitive load and to have comparable conditions in the two sessions. Both sessions were entirely performed using the robotic device and included an initial assessment (pre-fatigue), a fatiguing task and 4 post assessments (post-fatigue).

Figure 1 Design of experimental protocol. If stiffness was assessed on the first session (day 1), position sense was evaluated on the second, and vice versa.

Details of the protocol are shown in Figure 1. During each force assessment, subjects were asked: 1) to exert their maximum grip force (MVC_g) and 2) to perform two repetitions of their maximum voluntary isometric wrist contraction in the flexion ($MVIC_f$) and extension ($MVIC_e$) directions. Then, either wrist stiffness or position sense was evaluated according to the chosen daily session. The temporal duration of the two assessments was comparable (~ 2.5 min). Wrist stiffness was assessed through the delivery of position-controlled disturbances in wrist flexion-extension and computed through a mechanical impedance model of the wrist joint [4]. These external perturbations were characterized by small amplitudes and fast velocity ($100^\circ/s$), causing rotation at the wrist joint of $\pm 10^\circ$ from the neutral position [4]. Throughout this assessment, the subject was

asked not to anticipate or resist the disturbance, and to assume a natural grasp. Position sense was tested with an active paradigm: firstly, target positions were haptically identified by moving towards a virtual wall placed along the flexion direction. Then, after being brought back to the neutral position, subjects had to replicate the previously assumed joint configuration. Each target position was randomly chosen using a gaussian distribution centered at $15^\circ (\pm 1^\circ)$. During the fatigue task, subjects were asked to perform continuous reaching movements along the FE DoF against a constant torque exerted by the robotic device. This resistive torque opposed flexion and facilitated extension movements to the neutral posture and was tailored to 60% of each subject $MVIC_f$, assessed at the pre-fatigue force assessment. Specifically, starting from the neutral wrist position, subjects were asked to perform flexion movements to targets placed at 45° , as fast as possible. Since subjects were blindfolded, targets were perceived through both haptic walls and audible feedback. Three sounds could be presented to subjects during each trial: a “beep”, a “hold” or “release” warning. The latter two alerted subjects to slightly modify their grasp on the handle since it was falling outside the range of [70-80] % of MVC_g . For each flexion movement, the sEMG signals were band-pass filtered (10-450 Hz) and the corresponding mean frequency (F_{mean}) computed. A real-time algorithm was implemented to detect when the F_{mean} of either FCR or FCU fell below 60% of the maximum F_{mean} reached during the task. When the desired threshold was reached, a trigger signal was sent to the robot and the task terminated automatically. After the fatigue task, subjects immediately performed both force and position sense (or stiffness) assessments. Lastly, we asked subjects to rate their perceived level of fatigue on a scale from 0 (“no fatigue”) to 10 (“severe fatigue”).

III. RESULTS

Repeated Measures Anovas were performed to inspect presence of differences among assessments (1 pre- and 4 post-fatigue assessments). Given the design of the algorithm, the F_{mean} of both flexors (FCR, FCU) decreased significantly after the fatigue assessment in post 1 ($p_{\text{tukey}} < 0.001$) and immediately returned to their initial values by post 2 (Figure 2). F_{mean} of ECR remained consistent across all sessions. After Tukey correction, neither $MVIC_f$ nor $MVIC_e$ presented significant differences among all assessments, while MVC_g decreased by 5.4% after the post 1 until the end of the sessions (post 1 vs post 2 $p_{\text{tukey}} = 0.048$, post 1 vs post 4 $p_{\text{tukey}} = 0.013$). These results were comparable between the 2 different sessions of the experimental protocol. Concerning the effects of fatigue on wrist position sense, statistical results and Tukey-corrected post-hoc tests revealed that the error between each target position and the corresponding matched position decreased from pre-fatigue to the post 2 session ($p = 0.047$). All remaining post assessments were not different than pre-fatigue. A mixed-model statistical analysis of stiffness reported a significant decrease from pre-, through middle-, to the end of post- sessions ($p < 0.001$), with a slight tendency to recover in the last post 4, where stiffness was no longer different from post 1. Furthermore, the mean rate of perceived fatigue given by subjects at the end of the task was 7.9 ± 0.9 and the average number of movements performed to reach the F_{mean} threshold was 63.4 ± 15.8 .

Figure 2 F_{mean} of FCR (red), FCU (green), ECR (blue) muscles across the assessment sessions.

IV. DISCUSSION

This work presented how robotic devices could be employed to enhance the robustness and reliability of a set of human wrist-related measures. A robotic protocol of assessment ensures safe, repeatable, and controlled conditions, leading to the knowledge of measuring the same variable among different subjects or time points. Specifically, by exploiting the temporal resolution offered by the robot (1 kHz), we were able to tightly control the timing among post-fatigue assessments, thereby monitoring fatigue-related changes and the progress of recovery over time. Analogously, its nominal spatial resolution (0.04°) was used to obtain accurate kinematics measurements. The accuracy of measurements, coupled with the possibility to tailor the task to the abilities of individual subjects, could be used to monitor the presence of safe conditions during the evaluation. Additionally, the set of measurable variables can be expanded by synchronizing the robot with other external devices, such as the sEMG system or further sensors. This allowed us to develop an algorithm to detect a comparable level of muscle fatigue. Differently from previous works [3], our fatigue protocol was not based on a subjective assessment of perceived effort, but relied on the detection of physiological changes in muscle activity. With this controlled experimental protocol, we demonstrated that our maximal isometric wrist force measurements were unaffected by the dynamic fatigue protocol. Rather, the fatigue protocol substantially affected the mechanical and sensorimotor properties of the wrist joint. However, we also showed that these changes were recovered about 15 minutes after the fatigue task (this was the time from the first to the last post assessment).

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